

to Ya alone (Equation 2). Equation 3 further shows that increasing pest injuries, specifically ShB and DH, are associated with more than a proportional reduction in yield. Equation 3 demonstrates more generally that the

attainable yield, which represents the production levels, interacts with pest injuries in the descriptive damage function generated by the two experiments. Our data to date show that production levels—yield outcome of

farmers' management practices, inputs, and environmental factors—interact with pest injuries in damage functions and must be considered in pest management. ■

A simple methodology for analyzing rice sheath blight (ShB) epidemiologic processes under semicontrolled conditions

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We developed a simple and reproducible methodology to study ShB epidemics under semicontrolled environmental conditions. It involves two basic components: 1) an analogue of a standing crop that can be manipulated according to the environmental variables being investigated, and 2) a probe that allows monitoring and quantification of ShB conduciveness in this manipulated environment.

The crop analogue is a quadrat of 3 × 3 hills (see figure). At maximum tillering stage, all hills in the quadrats except the center hill—are inoculated with a rice hull/grain mixture colonized by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn to serve as source plants. The center hill is removed after inoculation and replaced with a healthy trap plant that was grown in an adjacent, disease-free area. The trap plant serves as a probe. After 3 d of exposure, the trap plant is transferred into a pot. ShB severity is measured, and emerging infection points are counted. The procedure can be used in a series of replications and for several treatments. It can be repeated over time with successive batches of trap plants.

Leaf wetness duration can be manipulated by covering the quadrat with plastic cages for different amounts of time. Crop density can be varied by planting hills at different spacings. The number and position of ShB lesions in the canopy can be manipulated by varying the amount and positioning of the inoculum. Trap plants can be grown in plots with

different N input levels to vary their N content; and different varieties can also be compared.

Data are analyzed using repeated-measures ANOVA. The table shows the format of an ANOVA where the log-transformed number of ShB infection points is analyzed in an experiment with three replications, eight treatments, and three batches. The treatments represent different combinations of inoculum amount and positioning (see figure).

The results indicate that the positioning of inoculum has a significant effect on the number of infection points. Estimates of treatment means are T1: 122 a; T2: 64 b; T3: 82 a; T4: 111 a; T5: 37 b; T6: 147 a; T7: 150 a; and T8: 20 c, where values followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to DMRT

($p < 0.05$). Further comparison of means shows significantly less infection points when inoculum was placed at the stem level only. A two- to fourfold increase in infection points occurred when the inoculum was placed at the leaf level. Increasing the amount of inoculum from 2.5 to 5.0 g did not significantly increase the number of infection points. The number is significantly lower in the third batch than in the first two batches, suggesting a decline in infection efficiency over time. Spontaneous infections are measured on the control trap plants (T8), which provide a measure of the 'background noise' specific to each experiment.

This methodology can be used to address several driving variables in the rice-ShB pathosystem. ■

Format of a repeated-measures ANOVA for the log-transformed number of infection points per trap plant. The experiment involves 5 replications, 8 treatments, and 3 batches.

Source of variation	df	Example			
		df	F_{obs}	$F_{0.05}$	Conservative $F_{0.05}^a$
Replication	r-1	4	6.23	2.71	2.71
Treatments (T) ^b	t-1	7	12.4	2.36	2.36
Control vs other treatments (U)	u-1	1	54.5	4.20	4.20
Among other treatments (V)	v-1	6	5.43	2.44	2.44
T7 vs T1 to T6 (W)	w-1	1	7.79	4.20	4.20
Among T1 to T6 (X)	x-1	5	4.96	2.56	2.56
Inoculum positioning (P)	p-1	2	11.6	3.34	3.34
Inoculum amount (A)	a-1	1	0.00	4.20	4.20
P × A	(p-1) (a-1)	2	12.4	3.34	3.34
Error (a)	(r-1) (t-1)	28			
Batch (B)	b-1	2	4.31	3.14	3.99
T × B	(t-1) (b-1)	14	1.68	1.85	2.15
(Control vs other treatments) × B	(u-1) (b-1)	2	4.90	3.14	3.99
(Among other treatments) × B	(v-1) (b-1)	12	1.14	1.90	2.24
(T7 vs T1 to T6) × B	(w-1) (b-1)	2	0.01	3.14	3.99
(Among T1 to T6) × B	(x-1) (b-1)	10	1.36	1.98	2.36
P × B	(p-1) (b-1)	4	2.88	2.51	3.14
A × B	(a-1) (b-1)	2	0.74	3.14	3.99
P × A × B	(p-1) (a-1) (b-1)	4	3.1	2.51	3.14
Error (b)	t (r-1) (b-1)	64			

^aBased on batch df = 1. The conservative F values are usually considered. ^bThe treatments represent different combinations of amount and positioning of inoculum: T1: 2.5 g at leaf level, T2: 2.5 g at stem level, T3: 2.5 g at stem level and 2.5 g at leaf level, T4: 5.0 g at leaf level, T5: 5.0 g at stem level, T6: 5.0 g at stem level and 5.0 g at leaf level, T7: 5.0 g at stem level and 2.5 g at leaf level, and T8: control.

Design for analyzing rice ShB epidemiologic processes under second-controlled environmental conditions.

Maximum diseased leaf area (DLA): a new parameter for leaf blast (BI) severity

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BI disease, caused by *Pyricularia grisea* Sacc., is evaluated in many experiments. Leaf BI is often assessed three or more times on the same plot within a season. Epidemiological studies require exact disease assessment, which is labor-intensive. The percentage DLA, a parameter commonly used, can be assessed visually with sufficient precision by a well-trained person using standard diagrams.

We analyzed data sets of two experiments in upland rice with the aim to reduce the labor required for disease assessment. Leaf BI was assessed visually on five fully developed leaves of 20 tillers/plot for 72 plots.

Leaf BI progress followed a typical pattern (Fig. 1). Depending on meteorological conditions, initial disease symptoms appeared 15-25 d after seeding (DAS) (on Zadoks' scale of growth, stage 15, 20/18, 22), followed by a progressive increase in disease severity. The peak in the progress curve occurred at 40-50 DAS. A steep decrease in severity was

1. Typical pattern of leaf BI progress.

observed thereafter and an initial low was reached about 70-80 DAS. This pattern was confirmed during several years of field experiments in the Philippines.

Fertilizer application and various upland cultivars (UPLRi-5, C22, Kinandang Patong, and IR47686-6-2-2-1) showed a synchronous disease progress (Fig. 1). A close linear relationship ($r^2 = 0.99$, $n = 72$, based on data range of 0-60% DLA) between the maximum DLA and area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) was observed (Fig. 2). Comparing treatment means for AUDPC and for maximum DLA yielded the same result.

Using the maximum DLA as a parameter for leaf BI severity proved to be a reliable and practical method in

2. Relation of AUDPC and values of maximum DLA for leaf BI.

several field experiments. The sensitive response of the disease progress to meteorological conditions—especially at the early vegetative stage when rice plants are extremely susceptible to BI—requires continuous monitoring of actual disease intensity in control plots. This procedure enables the researcher to predict the time of maximum disease severity.

Weather conditions and cultivar resistance can alter leaf BI progress. Comparing data from various sites and rice cultures using maximum DLA needs further investigation. Researchers are encouraged to test the parameter under their specific site conditions. ■